

TECHNICAL ADVANCE

Multi-class plant hormone HILIC-MS/MS analysis coupled with high-throughput phenotyping to investigate plant–environment interactions

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SUMMARY

Plant hormones are chemical signals governing almost every aspect of a plant's life cycle and responses to environmental cues. They are enmeshed within complex signaling networks that can only be deciphered by using broad-scale analytical methods to capture information about several plant hormone classes simultaneously. Methods used for this purpose are all based on reversed-phase (RP) liquid chromatography and mass spectrometric detection. Hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC) is an alternative chromatographic method that performs well in analyses of biological samples. We therefore developed and validated a HILIC method for broad-scale plant hormone analysis including a rapid sample preparation procedure; moreover, derivatization or fractionation is not required. The method enables plant hormone screening focused on polar and moderately polar analytes including cytokinins, auxins, jasmonates, abscisic acid and its metabolites, salicylates, indoleamines (melatonin), and 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC), for a total of 45 analytes. Importantly, the major pitfalls of ACC analysis have been addressed. Furthermore, HILIC provides orthogonal selectivity to conventional RP methods and displays greater sensitivity, resulting in lower limits of quantification. However, it is less robust, so procedures to increase its reproducibility were established. The method's potential is demonstrated in a case study by employing an approach combining hormonal analysis with phenomics to examine responses of three *Arabidopsis* ecotypes toward three abiotic stress treatments: salinity, low nutrient availability, and their combination. The case study showcases the value of the simultaneous determination of several plant hormone classes coupled with phenomics data when unraveling processes involving complex cross-talk under diverse plant–environment interactions.

Keywords: plant hormone, hydrophilic interaction chromatography, mass spectrometry, technical advance, high-throughput phenotyping, multifactorial plant stress, ACC, melatonin.

INTRODUCTION

Hormones are chemical messengers that transfer information between cells. Plant hormones, or phytohormones, are an assortment of low molecular weight compounds with diverse physicochemical properties. In land plants, there are at least nine classes of plant hormones: abscisic acid (ABA) and its metabolites (collectively ABAs), auxins (Aux), brassinosteroids (BRs), cytokinins (CKs), ethylene

(ET), gibberellins (GAs), jasmonic acid and its metabolites (JAs), salicylic acid and its metabolites (SAs), and strigolactones (SLs). These compounds govern many, if not all, internal processes within plants including cell division, elongation, and differentiation. In addition, they regulate physiological processes, resource and water management, and responses to pathogens and other environmental stimuli (Cutler & Nelson, 2017). The current list of plant

hormones is probably incomplete and will thus expand as newly (re)discovered compounds are shown to display phytohormone characteristics. Accordingly, several compound classes with potential roles in plant signaling have attracted considerable interest in recent years, including indoleamines (notably melatonin) and apocarotenoids (Arnao & Hernández-Ruiz, 2019; Back, 2021; Moreno et al., 2021); it will be interesting to see whether these substances eventually become classified as plant hormones. In addition, reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS) belong to the set of indispensable signaling molecules that play important roles during development and responses to exogenous stimuli (Devireddy et al., 2021; Gupta et al., 2022), furthermore, small peptide hormones such as systemin and phytosulfokine have been regarded as plant hormones for decades but have been less thoroughly studied than other plant hormone classes (Davies, 2010; Xin et al., 2020).

Plant hormones do not function in isolation; rather, they act as components of highly interconnected systems that enable nuanced responses to stimuli. Within these systems, plant hormones engage in a crosstalk, which allows the action of one phytohormone to influence the action of others (Aerts et al., 2021). This influence may involve regulating hormone biosynthesis, catabolism, transport, signal perception, or signal transduction. For example, the interplay between the major Aux, indole-3-acetic acid (IAA), and SLs shapes shoot architecture (Omoarelojie et al., 2019). Another example is fruit maturation and ripening, which are governed by the complex and dynamic relationships of GAs, ABA, ET, and Aux (Fenn & Giovannoni, 2021). To understand and decipher these complex interactions of plant hormones, one must acquire information about several (or all) plant hormone classes simultaneously. It is also helpful to gather information about related compounds such as biosynthetic precursors, catabolites, and transport forms of active hormones, which can provide additional clues about potential changes in hormone biosynthesis, catabolism, or transport. Gathering such information requires analytical methods capable of simultaneously quantifying many hormones and related metabolites, and the demands placed upon these methods become more stringent as new classes of target analytes are added.

Plant hormones are currently quantified using a variety of methods based on liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) with solid-phase extraction (SPE) during sample preparation (Tarkowská et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2020). SPE is vital for analyte enrichment because plant hormones are present at extremely low concentrations *in vivo* and for matrix removal to prevent signal suppression. MS/MS detection is predominantly based on triple quadrupole mass analyzers to ensure sufficient selectivity and high sensitivity, but it is becoming

increasingly common for high-resolution mass spectrometry systems to be used for quantitative analysis of plant hormones (Kisiala et al., 2019; Tillmann et al., 2021; Vrobel & Tarkowski, 2023). LC offers several chromatographic modes for the separation of diverse analytes. Reversed-phase (RP) chromatography is the most commonly used of these modes due to its ease of use, robustness, applicability, and predictability. Its dominance is especially pronounced in plant hormone analysis, where other chromatographic modes are very rarely used.

Hydrophilic interaction chromatography (HILIC) is an alternative chromatographic method for LC. Its popularity has been increasing steadily, and it has found applications as a complementary technique to conventional RP chromatography in fields including metabolomics, proteomics, and food or drug analysis (Buszewski & Noga, 2012; Marubini et al., 2018; Pezzatti et al., 2020). HILIC complements RP because it can retain and separate polar compounds, for which RP is inherently unsuitable. It does this by using stationary phases typically used in normal phase chromatography with solvents more commonly used in RP, although water is a stronger eluent in HILIC mode than in RP chromatography. The combination of an organic-rich solvent (typically acetonitrile) with a polar stationary phase creates a unique environment that gives rise to complex interactions. One interaction contributing significantly to retention is analyte partitioning between the bulk mobile phase and a water-rich stagnant layer formed on the surface of the stationary phase. Electrostatic interactions and hydrogen bonding between analytes and the stationary phase may also contribute to the separation mechanism (McCalley, 2017).

This complex separation mechanism means that HILIC can retain nonpolar and moderately polar compounds as well as polar ones (Čavar Zeljković et al., 2024; Periat et al., 2016; Periat, Boccard, et al., 2013), enabling the separation of a broad spectrum of analytes. Furthermore, many different stationary phases are available including bare silica, zwitterionic, diol, cyano, amino, and amide phases (Jandera, 2011). This makes it possible to tailor the analytical conditions to facilitate separation of analytes that are otherwise difficult to retain or separate. In addition to its unique selectivity profile, HILIC offers improved ionization and higher signal intensities when coupled to electrospray-MS due to the high organic content of the mobile phase (Periat, Boccard, et al., 2013). Increased sensitivity is especially valuable when analyzing trace substances such as plant hormones.

An impressive range of methods for quantitative plant hormone analysis have been developed (reviewed in Tarkowská et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2020), providing a wide variety of SPE procedures for plant hormone isolation and derivatization agents to facilitate detection (Vrobel & Tarkowski, 2023). However, to our surprise, only two methods

developed over a decade ago have used HILIC for the analysis of CKs (Liu et al., 2010, 2012), and only very recently HILIC was employed to analysis of ACC in plant samples (Cao et al., 2024). We therefore explored the limits and possibilities of HILIC, leading to the development and validation of a method suitable for the analysis of Aux, CKs, ABAs, JAs, SAs, indoleamines, and 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC) in a single sample without the need for derivatization. Importantly, the use of HILIC yielded considerable increases in analytical sensitivity and signal intensities, leading to low detection limits. The method was also carefully optimized for ACC analysis, making it possible to analyze a broad spectrum of analytes using a simple and rapid extraction protocol. Furthermore, the capabilities of the method were demonstrated in a case study to provide insights into the differential hormonal changes and physiological responses of three *Arabidopsis* ecotypes to joined abiotic stressors by a combined approach of phenomics and multiclass plant hormone analysis. In their natural habitat, plants experience simultaneous action of several abiotic stressors. However, researchers often study the effect of these stressors in the plants independently; thus, usually fail to capture unique plants' responses induced by the multifactorial stressors. Such combinations are, for example, drought accompanied by temperature extremes, drought and salinity, or salinity and nutrient deficiency (Suzuki et al., 2014; Zandalinas et al., 2021). The latter situation is represented in the case study to inspect the differential hormonal regulation and to highlight the dichotomy in plants' prioritization and decision-making in response to these combined stressors. Each condition, salinity and nutrient deficiency, necessitates an opposite reaction: either to uptake nutrients along with high salt concentration, leading to toxic effects, or to suppress uptake and face nutrient deficiency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

General strategy

Chromatographic separation using HILIC enables the analysis of polar compounds that are difficult to separate using RP chromatography. Importantly, HILIC also permits retention and separation of nonpolar and hydrophobic compounds through interactions with the stationary phase such as hydrogen bonding or electrostatic interactions (Greco & Letzel, 2013; McCalley, 2015). As broad spectrum of analytes as possible was therefore tested resulting in a method that encompasses analysis of CKs, Aux, JAs, SAs, ABAs, ACC, and indoleamines, but also shows that the developed method can be used to analyze GAs. This set of analytes includes basic (CKs, indoleamines), acidic (ABAs, Aux, JAs, SAs), (electro)neutral polar (ACC, ABA-glucose ester), and neutral moderately polar (melatonin, indole-3-acetamide) compounds; all analytes are listed in Table S1.

A downside of capturing such a wide spectrum of plant hormones is that complex sample enrichment protocols cannot be used because they would cause excessive loss of some analytes. Sample enrichment removes matrix components based on physicochemical properties; a wider spectrum of analytes' physicochemical properties implies that fewer matrix components could be removed.

Sample extraction and enrichment

Several extraction solvents have previously been used for multiclass hormone analysis including 100% ACN (Cai et al., 2019) and a modified Bielecki solvent (Dobrev & Kamínek, 2002; Kojima et al., 2009). In this work, a 7:2:1 mixture of ACN:H₂O:isopropanol (ACN:H₂O:IPA) was used because it is milder than the modified Bielecki solvent and enables extraction of a wide spectrum of compounds including polar analytes, unlike 100% ACN.

A sample enrichment procedure based on a modified mixed-mode cation exchange SPE protocol that has been used for decades (Dobrev & Kamínek, 2002; Kojima et al., 2009) was chosen because it was expected that acidic hormones would be retained hydrophobically in their protonated forms at low pH (~2) while weak bases such as CKs and ACC that span a wide range of polarities would be retained via electrostatic interactions. A single washing step with water was then performed to remove polar contaminants with minimal elution of weakly retained analytes and to remove residual acid to prevent the formation of ammonium formate during elution. It was necessary to avoid high salt concentrations as they caused the sample diluent to separate into immiscible components during sample reconstitution. An overview of the sample preparation procedure is presented in Figure 1.

Solvent incompatibility and diluent composition

A disadvantage of HILIC compared to RP is that it is subject to more pronounced solvent effects (Nováková et al., 2014) because of the high content of protic solvents in the sample diluent and/or the use of high injection volumes. Protic solvents, including simple alcohols, are hydrogen-bond donors that interact with the stationary phase and stagnant water layer, influencing the separation mechanism. This can cause peak shape distortion, broadening, or double peak formation. Using 100% ACN as the diluent eliminates this solvent effect and provides sharp, undistorted peaks (Heaton & McCalley, 2016; Ruta et al., 2010), but it does not dissolve polar compounds. In our case, increasing the diluent's water content to 10% or more led to a significant solvent effect. Various solvent mixtures of ACN, simple alcohols (methanol, ethanol, isopropanol—IPA), and buffers were therefore tested, leading to the discovery that a 1:2:10 mixture of 30 mM pH 3.0 ammonium formate buffer:IPA:ACN enabled complete analyte dissolution with no or minimal solvent effects. A high ACN content was

Figure 1. Overview of the sample preparation procedure. Color scheme reflects visual appearance of processed leaf samples.

needed to avoid solvent effects, and IPA was added to increase solubility. IPA was used in preference to the other simple alcohols that were tested because it has the lowest hydrogen-bond donor capacity and the least impact on separation (McCalley, 2017; Nováková et al., 2014).

Development of chromatographic separation

Each tested column (details in Experimental section —HILIC-MS/MS) provided a different selectivity profile, and the Acquity BEH Amide, Acquity BEH HILIC, and Kinetex HILIC columns all retained a majority of the selected analytes. The Luna NH₂ column offered excellent retention and peak shape for acidic plant hormones, but its

retention of bases and neutral compounds was unsatisfactory, while the Luna CN column gave unsatisfactory results with low retention in general, broad peaks, and no separation of CK isomers. The Acquity BEH Amide column was selected for method development because it achieved acceptable retention of all analytes (i.e., it exceeded the minimum retention of 1.5× the column dead volume) with satisfactory CKs isomer separation.

Bases (CKs) and neutral compounds were strongly retained on the Acquity BEH Amide column. However, to achieve sufficient retention of semi-polar acidic hormones (ABAs, JAs, SA, Aux, GAs), it was necessary to minimize the water content and raise the pH of the mobile phase. These considerations prompted the development of Method A5.5, which uses a mobile phase consisting of ammonium acetate buffer pH 5.5 at a final concentration of 5 mM in 95% ACN at 30 °C with a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min at the beginning of the gradient. The retention of acidic hormones and early eluting compounds was weakened by reducing the ACN content or pH, and by raising the buffer concentration, or temperature. A flow rate of 0.3 mL/min was selected to strike a balance between signal intensity and peak width. Method B3.0 (5 mM ammonium formate pH 3.0) was designed to facilitate analysis of compounds that do not ionize or ionize poorly at pH 5.5, including a subset of CKs, Aux, ACC, and indoleamines. In addition, the lower pH of the eluent in this case improved the ionization of several compounds in positive mode. Chromatograms obtained with both final methods are shown in Figure 2. While good results were obtained for most of the 49 target analytes, 4 CK nucleotides were not efficiently resolved by either HILIC method, which is perhaps unsurprising since analysis of these compounds is inherently problematic (Béres et al., 2010). The CK nucleotides were strongly retained and exhibited extreme peak broadening and tailing, meaning that the HILIC method is unsuitable for their analysis. RP chromatography thus remains the preferred choice for analysis of these compounds, despite their weak retention and poor ionizability in RP mode. The chromatographic behavior of all analytes is summarized in Table S2.

HILIC and RP comparison

Using different chromatographic modes has both advantages and disadvantages. At present, RP chromatography is the dominant tool used in plant hormone analysis (Tarkowská et al., 2014; Vrobel & Tarkowski, 2023; Wang et al., 2020). Consequently, it is important to show how the HILIC method differs from RP chromatography in terms of sensitivity, selectivity, and general robustness when analyzing these compounds. To highlight those differences only brought by the chromatographic mode, a series of analyses were performed on the same instrument, columns with similar dimensions, utilizing identical flowrate,

Figure 2. Chromatograms generated using Method A5.5 and Method B3.0. Bold lines correspond to quantifier transitions, lighter lines correspond to qualifiers. Zoomed-in regions highlight compounds with low signal intensities. (1) melatonin (MLT); (2) indole-3-acetamide (IAM); (3) 12-oxo-phytodienoic acid (OPDA); (4) salicylic acid (SA); (5) isopentenyladenine (iP); (6) isopentenyladenosine (iPR); (7) indole-3-butyric acid (IBA); (8) jasmonic acid (JA); (9) phenylpyruvic acid (PPyA); (10) abscisic acid (ABA); (11) abscisic acid glucose ester (ABA-GE); (12) cis-zeatin (cZ); (13) trans-zeatin (tZ); (14) indole-3-acetic acid (IAA); (15) dihydrozeatin (DHZ); (16) jasmonoyl-isoleucine (JA-Ile); (17) phenylacetic acid (PAA); (18) benzoic acid (BA); (19) neophaseic acid (NeoPA); (20) cis-zeatin riboside (cZR); (21) trans-zeatin riboside (tZR); (22) gibberellin A4 (GA4); (23) phaseic acid (PA); (24) dihydrozeatin riboside (DHZR); (25) phenylethylamine (PEA); (26) isopentenyladenine-9-glucoside (iP9G); (27) tryptamine (TRA); (28) isopentenyladenine-7-glucoside (iP7G); (29) gibberellin A3 (GA3); (30) dihydrophaseic acid (DPA); (31) 2-oxo-indole-3-acetic acid (OxIAA); (32) cis-zeatin-9-glucoside (cZ9G); (33) dihydrozeatin-9-glucoside (DHZ9G); (34) trans-zeatin-9-glucoside (tZ9G); (35) cis-zeatin-7-glucoside and cis-zeatin-O-glucoside (coeluting) (cZ7G + cZOG); (36) trans-zeatin-7-glucoside (tZ7G); (37) trans-zeatin-O-glucoside (tZOG); (38) cis-zeatin-O-glucoside riboside (cZROG); (39) trans-zeatin-O-glucoside riboside (tZROG); (40) salicylic acid glucoside (SAG); (41) indole-3-acetic acid-alanine (IAA-Ala); (42) indole-3-acetic acid-aspartic acid (IAA-Asp); (43) indole-3-acetic acid-glutamic acid (IAA-Glu); (44) serotonin (SRT); (45) 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (ACC).

and the same settings of the ion source. Four simple chromatographic separations based on simple 15 min identical scout gradients were used to compare two RP methods, RP1^{FA} and RP2^{AcA}, to two HILIC methods, HL1^{FA} and HL2^{AcA} (FA and AcA denoting formate buffer and acetate buffer, respectively). LLOQ for each method were obtained by analyzing standard solutions of all included in the comparison and generating calibration models for each method.

Both RP methods retained a higher number of analytes than the HILIC methods. However, while each HILIC method had its own unique shortcomings—for example, HL1^{FA} did not retain acids and several compounds were poorly ionized when analyzed using HL2^{AcA}—these shortcomings did not overlap. Combined analysis (2 injections per sample) using both HILIC methods thus provided coverage of the full range of tested analytes with the exception of CK nucleotides. The comparison also showed that the distribution coefficient (LogD) values of the analytes correlated positively with retention time (Rt) in RP mode but negatively in HILIC mode (Figure 3a). The complementarity of the two HILIC methods is illustrated in Figure 3b, which shows that the retention times of compounds analyzed using HL1^{FA} and HL2^{AcA} were significantly influenced by the pH difference between the two methods and were not strongly correlated, in contrast to the case for RP1^{FA} and RP2^{AcA}. Additionally, the HILIC retention times were very weakly correlated with those for the RP methods,

underscoring the orthogonality of the two chromatographic techniques and suggesting that they could be employed simultaneously in the analysis of plant hormones, in accordance with the increasingly common trend of using multiple methods or injections when performing broad-scale analysis (Kojima et al., 2009; Salem et al., 2020; Schäfer et al., 2016; Šimura et al., 2018; Xin et al., 2020).

To assess the sensitivity of the HILIC methods, LLOQs were calculated for all compounds instead of just comparing peak areas. This was done because the peak area depends on the peak shape and the tuning intervals of the instrument's detector. In keeping with the results of (Pariat, Bocard, et al., 2013), the combined HILIC methods outperformed the RP methods; compared to RP1^{FA}, they provided lower LLOQs for 63% of the compounds, similar LLOQs for 24%, and higher LLOQs for 17%. Compared to RP2^{AcA}, the HILIC methods provided lower LLOQs for 61% of the compounds, similar LLOQs for 18%, and higher LLOQs for 21% (Figure 3c). Low LLOQs are crucial for trace and ultra-trace analysis, so the HILIC methods offer possibilities of analyzing plant hormones using smaller quantities of plant material while providing better results than RP separation without needing to upgrade existing mass spectrometry instrumentation.

A disadvantage of HILIC is that it may be less robust than RP due to the presence of multiple factors influencing the separation mechanism (Heaton & McCalley, 2016;

Figure 3. (a) Correlation of LogD and retention times (Rt) in methods I, II, III and IV. (b) Scatterplot showing Rt correlations between the RP and HILIC methods; no difference was observed between the RP methods, but the HILIC methods show some complementarity. The lowest correlation was observed between HILIC and RP. (c) Histograms showing that the combined HILIC methods provided lower LLOQs than the RP methods.

McCalley, 2015, 2017; Periat et al., 2016; Periat, Grand-Guillaume Perrenoud, & Guillaume, 2013; Ruta et al., 2010). To achieve high reproducibility, it is necessary to maintain a consistent buffered mobile phase composition, pH, and equilibration time (Et) while minimizing the injection volume. A relatively long Et is necessary in HILIC mode because its separation efficiency depends partly on the formation of a stagnant water-rich layer over the stationary phase, and reaching full equilibrium may take several hours or even a whole day. However, full equilibration is not necessary because good performance and reproducible results can be obtained at partial equilibrium (McCalley, 2020; Nováková et al., 2014). Before running sequence analyses, a stored column was equilibrated for exactly 120 min with the initial mobile phase, after which two blank runs were done. The Et between runs had profound effects on the Rt of most analytes and had to be optimized.

Both Method A5.5 and Method B3.0 use an Et corresponding to partial equilibration in order to strike a balance between maintaining a reasonably short gap between analytical runs and obtaining satisfactory analyte elution patterns. The difference between LC systems using binary or quaternary pumps is worth mentioning. Due to the increased extra-column volume of the quaternary pump systems, longer Et between analytical runs might be necessary to achieve the same results as with binary pumps.

Methods validation

The method was validated in terms of lower and upper limits of quantification (LLOQ and ULOQ), linear dynamic range, precision and accuracy, and process efficiency (PE). The LLOQ was defined as the calibration point for which the error of the back-calculated concentration was within $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal concentration in accordance with the ICH harmonized guideline for bioanalytical methods (EMA/CHMP/ICH/172948, 2019). PE provides a combined magnitude of recovery (losses during sample preparation) and matrix effects (ionization suppression or enhancement) as outlined by Matuszewski et al. (2003).

The method's LLOQ, ULOQ, and linear dynamic range were evaluated by constructing a calibration model with nine concentration levels spanning 4.5 orders of magnitude between the upper and lower limits of the instrument. A stock solution containing all standards was prepared in 1:1 H₂O:DMF solvent and diluted sequentially with sample diluent to form concentration series 100, 30, 10, 3, etc. while retaining identical concentrations of IS. Calibration curves were constructed after log-log transformation to increase accuracy and robustness and to avoid leveraging effects in the multi-order calibration model (Singtoroj et al., 2006). The concentrations of standards in the stock solution were chosen either based on the available quantity of the standard compound (only quantities in the μg range were available for some commercially available substances, placing an upper limit on the achievable concentration) or to prevent detector saturation. The LLOQs and linear dynamic ranges for the analytes are listed in Table S3; CKs had the lowest LLOQs (down to 30 amol on injection), while ACC had the highest LLOQ (3 pmol). The log-log calibration models were linear over several orders of magnitude in concentration; in some cases their linear range spanned 4.5 orders of magnitude, matching the instrumental range. These LLOQs for the majority of analytes are in the same order of magnitude as reported by previously published works of (Cai et al., 2019; Šimura et al., 2018; Xin et al., 2020); therefore, suggesting comparable performance of the methods. However, such a simple comparison fails to acknowledge the differences introduced by different performances of mass spectrometers and by different definitions of LLOQ; this presented work diverts from utilizing signal-to-noise ratio in favor of the

recently adopted EMA ICH approach to calculate LLOQ. Such difficulty in comparing various methods was one of the reasons we conducted HILIC and RP comparisons in this work. Accuracy was tested by spiking samples (pre-extraction) at three different concentration levels (chosen to match three of the calibration points) and back-calculating to nominal concentrations. In all cases, the calculated bias was within the interval from -15% to $+15\%$, demonstrating that the method's accuracy was satisfactory (see Table S4). To evaluate reproducibility, the precision of intraday and interday measurements of plant samples was calculated; Table S5 shows that reproducibility was also satisfactory, with the error being below 15% in all cases except for one where it reached 16.8%. These results show that the developed method is accurate and precise over several orders of magnitude in analyte concentration. Although serotonin, IAA aspartate, and glutamate conjugates could be separated by HILIC, these compounds exhibited limited stability during sample preparation. Common additives such as butylated hydroxytoluene or diethyldithiocarbamate (Pěňčík et al., 2009) did not resolve this problem and had additional negative effects on chromatographic separation.

PE was evaluated by adding the IS solution to samples containing 1.2, 2.4, and 4.8 mg DW (20, 40, and 80 mg FW equivalents) of plant material before extraction and comparing the peak areas of all IS in the matrix and in the standard solution. For samples containing 1.2 mg DW of plant material, the PE ranged from 13.3 to 2988.9% (median 90.4%) for Method A5.5 and from 7.9 to 217.3% (median 57.1%) for Method B3.0. Higher quantities of plant material altered the matrix effects, causing the PE to increase for 60% of the IS in Method A5.5. However, such increases were only observed for 20% of the IS in Method B3.0. In both cases, the PE of the remaining IS decreased when the quantity of plant material was increased. In almost all cases, increasing the quantity of extracted plant material increased the analyte content of the extract to a degree that outweighed any reduction in PE, leading to an increase in signal intensity. This net benefit was observed for every analyte bar one (Table S6). Although performance was acceptable with all tested quantities of plant material, the best results were obtained using samples containing 4.8 mg DW (80 mg FW), which gave the highest signal intensity and the best precision, presumably due to lower weighing error and easier handling (Table S6). This finding partially contradicts the many recent reports that miniaturizing sample preparation procedures can improve performance (Cai et al., 2019; Pěňčík et al., 2018; Šimura et al., 2018; Včelářová et al., 2021) and suggests that miniaturization may be unnecessary when ample plant material is available. In cases where only small sample masses are available (~ 10 mg FW and less), wide-scale plant hormone screening may be inherently unsuitable, making it

preferable to use targeted single-class analyses that require derivatization (Cai et al., 2019; Tarkowská et al., 2014; Vrobel & Tarkowski, 2023).

Caveats of ACC analysis

ACC plays a double role as a signaling molecule and a ET precursor (Li et al., 2022). Despite the prominent role, this compound remained often neglected due to its chemical properties which prevent easy analysis by LC-MS in RP mode or GC-MS; chemical derivatization is needed to increase its volatility in the case of GC and to reduce its polarity in the case of RP-LC, reviewed in Vrobel and Tarkowski (2023). HILIC provides a convenient way to analyze this compound without prior derivatization. Of the two methods developed in this work, Method B3.0 is more suitable for ACC analysis because its pH 3 eluent causes protonation of the ACC carboxyl group, enabling positive mode ionization of an otherwise electroneutral compound.

During the initial stages of method development, the results obtained for ACC were unpromising: the signals of the IS D4-ACC were unexpectedly orders of magnitude higher in plant material than in standard solutions. It was later discovered that endogenous serine coeluted with D4-ACC and thus cross-contributed to D4-ACC signal. Moreover, the MRM transitions of D4-ACC and serine were indistinguishable due to the low resolution of QQQ analyzers (Figure 4a). To overcome this problem, the chromatographic separation procedure was adjusted to improve the chromatographic resolution in a reasonable time-frame (Figure 4b). It is also possible to exploit the 106 \rightarrow 32 transition, to which serine does not contribute. However, the intensity of this transition was only 3% of that of the most intense 106 \rightarrow 60 transition. Given the low signal intensity and broad base of the D4-ACC peak, reliance on this transition is not ideal, but it is a serviceable option in cases where high endogenous serine levels interfere with the analysis (Figure 4c). Usability of 106 \rightarrow 32 transition was confirmed by the method validation, and this transition provides accurate results (Table S4) despite its limitations. ACC exhibited a wide peak base on all tested columns. Interestingly, though, the chromatographic adjustments developed to separate D4-ACC and serine also led to the separation of a previously unrecognized coeluting pair of unlabeled ACC and an unknown compound that cross-contributes to both MRM transitions of ACC (102 \rightarrow 56 and 102 \rightarrow 28). Conveniently, the method's chromatographic resolution allows reasonable peak integration despite this because the signal intensities of these two compounds are of the same order of magnitude. Alternatively, high-resolution mass spectrometry could be used to achieve sufficient selectivity to distinguish serine from D4-ACC, which would allow reliable quantification and also shorten the chromatographic run.

Figure 4. (a) Expected fragmentation spectra and intensities of qualifiers relative to quantifier transitions. (b) Chromatograms of ACC, D4-ACC and serine standards with magnification of the 106 → 32 transition (green). (c) Chromatograms of real samples showing the presence of 2 critical pairs: ACC and an unknown compound, and D4-ACC and serine.

The existence of these critical pairs highlights the value of good chromatographic separation. Native ACC has been analyzed in RP mode even though it exhibits no retention on RP columns (Griesser et al., 2020; Mhlongo et al., 2020; Riet et al., 2016; Xin et al., 2020). Coeluting compounds that are also not retained in RP such as serine and other unknown compound(s) could cause inaccurate quantification of ACC. The problem of possible cross-contribution of D4-ACC and serine has not been previously addressed, this includes the most recently developed methods (Cao et al., 2024; Karady et al., 2024). A recently published method aims at ACC quantification using derivatization agent 6-aminoquinolyl-N-hydroxysuccinimidyl carbamate selective toward amino acids (Karady et al., 2024), which includes the main contaminant, serine. However, based on the proposed reaction mechanism, the amino-quinoline derivatives of

D4-ACC and serine are expected to remain indistinguishable by QQQ analyzers. Therefore, the analysis of native ACC and possibly its derivatives by RP should be replaced by a more appropriate option such as HILIC. Apart from accurate quantification, HILIC also has the potential to analyze conjugated forms of ACC (Li et al., 2022; Van Poel & Van Der Straeten, 2014) and greatly facilitate research of these poorly explored compounds.

A case study

The method's capabilities for multiclass plant hormone screening, including polar, moderately polar, and charged analytes, were evaluated in a case study. Plants of three *Arabidopsis* ecotypes (Columbia—Col-0, Landsberg—Ler, and Wassilewskija—WS-2) plants were subjected to different stressors in a single or double combination: standard (FullMS) or low nutrient (1/3MS) and/or salt stress conditions (NaCl). Plants were grown for 14 days in 12-well plates as described in De Diego et al. (2017). This high-throughput screening *in vitro* approach simulates a more natural environment because the plants are grown without sucrose, and the plates are not hermetically sealed, allowing gas exchange. We believe that this approach provides an environment closer to the normal growth conditions of a plant and allows us to obtain more reliable and relevant data on plant responses. 1/3MS and NaCl conditions led to growth retardation of all ecotypes (Figure 5). Ler exhibited a substantial reduction in growth when compared to Col-0 and WS-2 under NaCl conditions. Combined 1/3MS + NaCl stress further increased severity, causing significant growth retardation in all ecotypes and higher mortality in Ler and WS-2 (Figure 5).

In total, 30 analytes were detected, with 22 being detected in all treatments (Tables S7–S9). The detected compounds included orphaned compounds such as ACC, phenylacetic acid (PAA), and melatonin (MLT), which have recently attracted attention in the plant science community. Multivariate statistical analysis (Figure 6a–f), including three principal component (PC) analyses and correlation matrices, was conducted to gain insights into the dataset. Firstly, we analyzed the effect of the single stressor in the three accessions (Figure 6a–d). Different responses between accessions were observed under nutritional and salt stress. For example, in Figure 6a, PC1, accumulating 54.4% of the model variance, mainly separated the plants grown under standard or low nutrition, independent of the accession. Only stressed Col-0 seedlings separated from the other two accessions due to a higher tolerance (lower mortality) to these growth conditions, as indicated by PC2 (an additional 20.1%). The high mortality of WS-2 and Ler positively correlated with the accumulation of specific analytes such as cZ, cZROG, and other cZ-type CKs and negatively with OxIAA and many fluorescence-related parameters; electron transport rate (ETR), Φ PSII, Fv/Fm and

Figure 5. Phenotypes of *Arabidopsis* seedlings subjected to a combination of treatments. FullIMS – control group; 1/3MS – nutrition deficiency induced by $\frac{1}{3}$ strength of MS media, NaCl – salinity induced by 75 mM NaCl, 1/3MS + NaCl – combination of nutrition deficiency and salinity.

Fv/Fm', and the green leaf index (GLI), as indicated the correlation matrix (Figure 6b). The accumulation of cZ and cZ-type CKs has been reported to be accumulated in various plant species under certain growth conditions that limit plant growth (Schäfer et al., 2015). Similarly, Silva-Navas et al. (2019) observed that increased cZ also occurred under Pi starvation. This may be because cZ is more related to plant growth than other biological processes, such as sink-source relations, as reported by Lacuesta et al. (2018). This study also showed that the leaves with higher cZ levels reduced their fluorescence efficiency (lower Φ PSII) and increased the non-photochemical quenching (NPQ) values, as observed in WS-2 and Ler accession. Regarding tZ- and iP- type CKs, tZ was consistently associated with better growth (total dry weight, absolute growth rate—AGR, relative growth rate—RGR) and photosynthetic capacity, while iP levels vary depending on growth conditions (Figure 6a,c).

Regarding OxIAA, Dziewit et al. (2021) observed its accumulation in *Arabidopsis* plants grown under high levels of NH_4^+ . They connect the accumulation with a growth limitation. This was partially true because the highest OxIAA levels accumulated in Col-0 under low nutritional conditions, which exhibited smaller plants than

those from this accession under optimal conditions (Figure 6a). However, when the interaction of nutrients and salt was analyzed (Figure 6a,c,e), the healthier and bigger plants had the highest OxIAA content. The results pointed to a strong influence of the interaction of the stresses as critical factor determining the plant response to the growth condition, particularly at the metabolic level.

ABA has been suggested to play a vital role in nitrate uptake in fluctuating N environments. However, the molecular mechanisms underlying the involvement of ABA in nutrient deficiency responses are unknown. A recent study published by Su et al. (2021) showed clear evidence that ABA and its signaling negatively regulated nitrate uptake. In our study, ABA accumulation was reduced in plants under nutritional stress (Figure 6a), likely as an attempt to improve nitrogen use efficiency under limited nutritional conditions. Inversely, salt-stressed plants accumulated the highest ABA values, mainly when grown with a complete MS medium (Figure 6c,d). ABA has been reported to mitigate the harmful effects of abiotic stress in plants by gene expression modulation, stomatal closure, formation of protective metabolites, and other adaptive biochemical processes (reviewed by Singh and Roychoudhury, 2023). Under salt stress conditions, ABA accumulation has been

Figure 6. (a) PCA biplot and (b) correlation matrix of the complete data set highlight correlations of hormonal changes and phenotypical changes of 17-day-old *Arabidopsis* seedlings under the influence of nutrient deficiency. (c) PCA biplot and (d) correlation matrix of the data set of acquired variables from the seedlings under a single salt stress treatment. (e) PCA biplot and (f) correlation matrix highlighting the changes in the seedlings under combined stressors (nutrient and salinity). ABA, abscisic acid; ABA.GE, abscisic acid glucose ester; ACC, 1-aminocyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid; AGR, absolute growth rate; BA, benzoic acid; cZ, *cis*-zeatin; cZ7G.cZOG, sum of *cis*-zeatin-7-glucoside and *cis*-zeatin-O-glucoside; cZR *cis*-zeatin riboside; cZR0G, *cis*-zeatin riboside-O-glucoside; DHZR, dihydrozeatin riboside; DPA, dihydrophaseic acid; DW_Percentage, plant dry content; DW_Plant, dry mass of the plant; ETR, electron transport rate; Fv_Fm; Fv_Fm.1 maximal quantum efficiency of photosystem II; GLL, green leaf index; IAA, indole-3-acetic acid; IAM, indole-3-acetamide; iP, isopentenyladenine; iP7G, isopentenyladenin-7-glucoside; iP9G, isopentenyladenin-9-glucoside; iPR, isopentenyladenosine; JA, jasmonic acid; JA.Ile, jasmonoyl-isoleucine; MLT, melatonin; NGRDI, normalized green red difference index; NPQ, non-photochemical quenching; OxIAA, 2-oxo-indole-3-acetic acid; PA, phaseic acid; PAA, phenylacetic acid; PEA, phenylethylamine; PhiPSII, effective quantum yield of photosystem II; RGR, relative growth rate; SA, salicylic acid; SAG, salicylic acid glucoside; tZ, *trans*-zeatin; tZ7G, *trans*-zeatin-7-glucoside; tZ9G, *trans*-zeatin-9-glucoside; tZOG, *trans*-zeatin-O-glucoside; tZR, *trans*-zeatin riboside; VARI, visible atmospheric resistant index.

reported to be crucial for inducing higher tolerance in plants (Prerostova et al., 2017). However, the experiments were done with plants grown in optimal nutrient conditions. In this regard, it is known that salinity soils are erosional terrains with poor structures, complicating nutrient retention and plant uptake (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023). Thus, in our study, the limited ABA accumulation in *Arabidopsis* seedlings under combined salt and low nutrition could help the plants increase nutrient uptake efficiency, potentially aiding their survival under this stressful growth condition. In this context, future experiments are needed to understand further the ABA role in the plant response to these combined stress conditions (low nutrition and salt) using different genotypes with varied strategies.

Finally, the strong correlation between MLT and NPQ, mainly accumulated in those stressed plants with higher survival levels (mainly Col-0), is worth mentioning (Figure 6b,d,f). These results contradict previous findings that observed reduced NPQ in salt-stressed plants after exogenous MLT application (Jiang et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2015). However, higher heat dissipation could be an excellent strategy to protect the photosystem and reduce plant damage under salinity (Pan et al., 2021), as could happen in salt-stressed Col-0 seedlings. In summary, the plants' responses to single and combined stressors induce different metabolic reactions, sometimes opposite to expected results. Further studies should combine growth conditions and accessions to understand the plant response and tolerance mechanisms better.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

We have developed and validated a novel HILIC-MS/MS method for rapid multi-class plant hormone analysis in plant samples with a fast sample preparation procedure. The method involves performing two chromatographic runs and allows broad-spectrum screening of CKs, Aux, JAs, ABAs, SAs, indoleamines (notably, melatonin), and orphaned hormones such as PAA and ACC in a single sample. In contrast to previously published multi-class plant hormone analysis methods (Cai et al., 2019; Kojima et al., 2009; Salem et al., 2020; Schäfer et al., 2016; Šimura

et al., 2018; Xin et al., 2020), such broad screening is achieved without derivatization or fractionation, which would otherwise prolong the entire analytical procedure. Additionally, HILIC has notable advantages over conventional RP chromatography including higher sensitivity and a different selectivity profile that facilitates separation of polar plant hormones. Its high sensitivity allows researchers to achieve LLOQ than with RP chromatography without needing to purchase new instruments. Care was taken to ensure high reproducibility and robustness during the method's development, which is important as these factors are often lacking in HILIC methods. As a result, the method presented here is a powerful standalone tool for broad screening and could serve as a basis for further development of plant hormone analysis methods. This could entail developing single-class analytical methods or complex protocols based on the isolation and successive chromatographic separation of several fractions, taking advantage of the orthogonal selectivities of HILIC and RP.

The potential of this novel method was demonstrated in a case study. An approach combining multiclass hormonal analysis with high-throughput phenotyping was utilized to gain insights into the response of three *Arabidopsis* accessions (Col-0, Ler, and WS-2) under single or combined stresses: salinity, low nutrition, or their combination. Col-0 seedlings exhibited a higher tolerance toward salinity stress compared to other ecotypes; higher mortality of Ler and WS-2 was associated with higher CKs content, predominantly cZ-type CKs and iP. Furthermore, the accumulation of ABA under combined stress was lower than under salinity stress alone, presumably to balance the nitrogen uptake-limiting effect of ABA under a nutrient-deficient environment. This result highlights the antagonistic role of ABA under single and combined stress conditions. Finally, the strong correlation of MLT content with NPQ under stress contradicts works reporting the effect of MLT on lowering the NPQ (Jiang et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2015). Further research in these areas is needed to describe undergoing processes. Nevertheless, these results indicate that the simultaneous determination of several plant hormone classes could be a valuable tool to provide further insights into the networks, cross-talk,

and dynamics of plant hormones in various plant-environment interactions.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Chemicals and materials

All plant hormone standards (a list of 49 compounds and their abbreviations is provided in Table S1) were purchased from OIChemIm (Olomouc, Czechia) unless otherwise specified. D5-jasmonic acid, ACC, PAA, phenylethylamine, benzoic acid, SA, tryptamine, serotonin, melatonin, GA3, and GA4 were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Dihydrophaseic acid, phaseic acid and their D3 analogs, and neophaseic acid were obtained from the National Research Council (Saskatoon, Canada). D4 analogues of tryptamine, serotonin, and melatonin were purchased from Cayman Chemicals Europe (Tallinn, Estonia). Solvents of LC-MS/MS purity (acetonitrile—ACN, methanol—MeOH, isopropanol—IPA) were purchased from Merck. NORMAPUR formic acid (FA) and acetic acid (AcA) were purchased from VWR International (Radnor, PA, USA). Water was purified with a MilliQ system (Milford, MA, USA), and ammonium hydroxide was purchased from Lach:NER (Neratovice, Czechia). SPE cartridges, Oasis MCX 30 mg, were purchased from Waters (Milford, MA, USA).

Plant material

Arabidopsis thaliana accession Col-0 plants were used for method development and validation. 21-day-old plants were grown in pots filled with substrate with a photo-period of 16/8 h at 22/20°C, 60% humidity, and photon irradiance of 110 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{sec}^{-1}$.

For the case study, three *Arabidopsis* accessions were grown in the indoor growth chamber: Columbia (Col-0), Landsberg (Ler), and Wassilewskija (WS-2), as described by (De Diego et al., 2017). Three-day-old seedlings were transferred onto 12-well plates containing full or 1/3 Murashige-Skoog (MS) media (Murashige & Skoog, 1962), with or without 75 mM NaCl (Salt), ending with three factors: Accession, Nutrient, and Salt. The plates were transferred to the Olophen platform (https://www.plant-phenotyping.org/db_infrastructure#/tool/57), equipped with the PlantScreen™ XYZ system. *Arabidopsis* seedlings were grown for 14 days under controlled conditions (22/20°C with a 16/8 h light/dark cycle, a photon irradiance of 120 μmol photons of PAR $\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{sec}^{-1}$, and 60% relative humidity).

The plates were photographed using RGB and FluorCam top-view cameras, and various morphological and physiological parameters were extracted. From the RGB images, different morphological traits such as area, perimeter, RGR, AGR, and three color-related indices, normalized green red difference index NGRDI, GLI and visible atmospherically resistant index (VARI), informing about the health were calculated according to (Ugena et al., 2018). At the end of the experiment, chlorophyll fluorescence-related parameters (Fv/Fm, Fv'/Fm', NPQ, and ΦPSII) were also estimated from the FluorCam images in the *Arabidopsis* seedling following the protocol described by (Sorrentino et al., 2021). After that, all samples were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen, and fresh weight was recorded during the sample collection. After lyophilization, dry weight was recorded, and samples were homogenized using a ball mill (mixer mill MM 400, RETSCH, Germany) for analysis.

Sample pretreatment

Up to 80 mg of fresh material (or the equivalent mass of lyophilized material; approximately in the range of 5–8 mg) was

extracted with 1 ml of extraction solvent (a 7:2:1 ACN:H₂O:IPA mixture) containing a mixture of stable isotope-labeled internal standards (IS) (120 fmol of cytokinin nucleosides IS, 1.2 pmol of remaining CKs and melatonin IS, 120 pmol Aux and jasmonic acid IS, 1.2 nmol of ACC and benzoic acid IS, and 12 pmol of remaining IS). Extraction was performed in an ice-cold ultrasonic bath for 30 min. After centrifugation (4°C, 20 000 *g*, 15 min), supernatants were transferred into new 2 ml tubes and evaporated *in vacuo*. Residues were reconstituted in 50 μl of MeOH, sonicated for 5 min, and 950 μl of 1 M FA was added. Samples were again sonicated for 5 min and centrifuged (4°C, 20 000 *g*, 20 min). The supernatant was loaded onto an equilibrated Oasis MCX column (activated with 1 ml MeOH, equilibrated with 1 ml 1 M FA), washed with 1 ml MilliQ water, eluted with 1.5 ml 1.34 M NH₄OH in 90% MeOH, and evaporated *in vacuo*. Dried residues were either stored at –20°C or reconstituted in 60 μl of sample diluent (a 1:2:10 mixture of aqueous buffer 30 mM FA pH 3.0, IPA, and ACN), sonicated for 15 min, filtered, transferred to a total recovery vial, and analyzed by HILIC-MS/MS. An overview of the sample pretreatment protocol is provided in Figure 1.

HILIC-MS/MS

In the early method development, five columns with different stationary phases sorbents were tested: Acquity BEH Amide 150 \times 2.1 mm 1.7 μm (Waters), Acquity BEH HILIC (silica) 150 \times 2.1 mm 1.7 μm (Waters), Kinetex HILIC (cross-linked diol) 150 \times 2.1 mm 2.6 μm (Phenomenex), Luna CN 150 \times 2.1 mm 3 μm (Phenomenex), and Luna NH2 150 \times 2.1 mm 3 μm (Phenomenex). Finally, Acquity BEH Amide column was selected for chromatographic separations. Each sample was used in two complementary analytical runs with different eluents to enable broad plant hormone analysis—Method A5.5 and Method B3.0 (the numbers denote the buffer pH). Method A5.5 used a binary gradient at a flow rate of 0.3 ml/min at 30°C with mobile phase A being 95% ACN containing 5 mM AcA (pH 5.5) and mobile phase B being 50% ACN containing 5 mM AcA (pH 5.5). The gradient profile was 0–1 min 0% B; 8 min 37% B; 9.2 min 66% B; 9.3 min 100% B; 11.8 min 100% B; 11.9 min 0% B; 26.0 min 0% B at 30°C. Method B3.0 used a binary gradient at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min at 30 °C with component A being 95% ACN containing 5 mM FA (pH 3.0) and component B being 50% ACN with 5 mM FA (pH 3.0). The gradient profile was 0–1 min 0% B; 12 min 77% B; 12.1 min 100% B, 15 min 100% B; 15.1 min 0% B; 26.5 min 0% B. The pH was adjusted with ammonia, and the buffer concentration at the final volume is listed. In all cases, the injected sample volume was 5 μl .

All analyses were performed on a Shimadzu (Kyoto, Japan) Nexera X2 modular LC system consisting of binary pumps LC-30 AD, autosampler SIL-30 AC, and column oven CTO-20 AC coupled to an MS-8050 mass spectrometer. Quantification was achieved by multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) in scheduled time windows. A list of all MRM transitions is provided in Table S2. The ion source was used in its default configuration with an interface voltage of 4 kV for positive mode and –3 kV for negative mode, DL temperature 250°C, interface temperature 300°C, heat block temperature 400°C, nebulizing gas flow rate 3 L/min, drying gas 10 L/min, and heating gas 10 L/min.

To highlight differences in selectivity and sensitivity between HILIC and RP, 4 illustrative scout gradient methods were set up; two for each mode. In RP mode, an Acquity CSH C18 column (150 \times 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) was used, and two methods were developed: RP1^{FA} and RP2^{AcA}. The mobile phase compositions were (I) A = 15 mM FA pH 3.0; B = ACN and (II) A = 10 mM AcA, B = ACN. Both methods used a gradient profile of 0–1 min 5% B, 16 min 100% B. In HILIC mode an Acquity BEH Amide column

(150 × 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) was used and two methods developed: HL1^{FA} and HL2^{AcA}. HL2^{AcA} used the same mobile phase composition as Method A5.5, and HL1^{FA} used the same mobile phase composition as Method B3.0 (see above). Both methods were run with a gradient profile of 0–1 min 0% B, 16 min 100% B. In all cases, the temperature was set to 30°C, and the flow rate was 0.3 ml/min. pH-dependent distribution coefficient (LogD) values for all analytes were retrieved from ChemAxon's (2023) [Chemicalize.com](https://www.chemicalize.com) [data retrieved: August 2023] at pH values 3.0, 3.5, and 5.5.

Data analysis

Raw data were processed using Shimadzu software LabSolutions v. 5.97 SP1. Statistical analyses were performed in R Studio software build 2023.12.1(R v. 4.3.3). The correlation matrix was constructed using the package *corrplot*, and missing values were handled by pairwise correlation. Significance tests at a confidence level of 0.99 were performed to identify statistically significant correlations. A principal component analysis biplot was generated using the *factoextra* package; data were scaled to unit variance and centered.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

OV original idea and conceptualization, method development, and validation, data analysis, original draft writing and editing; SCZ method development and validation, supervision, review, and editing JD method development and validation; LS case study design, funding acquisition, review, and editing; NDD case study design, high-throughput plant phenotyping, data analysis, review, and editing; PT supervision, funding acquisition, review, and editing. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors declare no financial competing interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional Supporting Information may be found in the online version of this article.

Table S1. A list of analytes used in this work.

Table S2. Retention times and mass spectrometry settings of all analytes.

Table S3. Analytes' LLOQ and ULOQ values.

Table S4. Analytical accuracy of the methods.

Table S5. Values of intra-day and inter-day precision.

Table S6. Process efficiency of the methods under variable sample amount.

Table S7. Case study data of Col-0 seedlings (measured concentration of analytes, plant weight, dry content and mortality).

Table S8. Case study data of Ler seedlings (measured concentration of analytes, plant weight, dry content and mortality).

Table S9. Case study data of WS-2 seedlings (measured concentration of analytes, plant weight, dry content and mortality).

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